

Data on zinc deficiency symptoms.^a Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	% of leaves affected		Intensity of leaf area affected (%)	
	AV	TV	AV	TV
Control	67.3	55.1	31.2	34.0
Azolla 10 t/ha	42.0	40.4	12.3	20.5
" 20 "	17.5	24.7	5.9	14.1
" 30 "	8.7	17.2	2.0	8.1
" 40 "	3.1	10.1	0.7	4.8
" 50 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 60 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 70 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 80 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 90 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
" 100 "	0.5	4.1	0.5	4.1
C.D. (P= 0.05%)		6.3	4.7	

^aAV = actual value of zinc deficiency worked out in percentage; TV = transformed value (angular value) of the percentage of zinc deficiency. Intensity of leaf areas affected = the area of the leaf covered by zinc deficiency symptoms.

deficiency symptom on the 25th DT for each treatment was recorded (see table).

Significant reduction in zinc deficiency was observed with azolla application from 10 t/ha onward compared to the untreated control. The deficiency

symptom was negligible at 40 t azolla/ ha and the crop was completely free from it at 50 t/ha and above. ■

Comparison of supergranules, sulfur-coated and ordinary urea in transplanted Jaya rice

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A field experiment compared the effectiveness of urea supergranules, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and ordinary urea at low to moderate levels of nitrogen application (see table). At 30 kg N/ ha, the supergranules proved significantly superior to the best split of ordinary urea but statistically at par with SCU. At higher levels of nitrogen application (60 and 90 kg N/ha), supergranules and SCU were not superior to the best split, but were definitely superior to single basal incorporation. ■

Effects of urea supergranules, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and ordinary urea on transplanted Jaya rice, Pantnagar, India, 1980 rainy season.^a

Nitrogen rate (kgN/ha)	Source and method of application ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	No nitrogen	2.5
30	Urea, best split	3.6
30	SCU, broadcast and incorporated, basal	4.1
30	Supergranules of urea, placed ^a 10-12 cm deep	4.3
60	Urea, best split	5.2
60	Urea, broadcast and incorporated, basal	4.2
60	SCU, broadcast and incorporated, basal	5.1
60	Supergranules of urea, placed 10-12 cm deep	5.3
90	Urea, best split	5.8
90	Urea, broadcast and incorporated, basal	4.3
90	SCU, broadcast and incorporated, basal	5.7
90	Supergranules of urea, placed 10-12 cm deep	5.7
		S.Em. ± 220
		C.D. (5%) 640
		C.V.(%) 9

^aNursery sowing: June. ^bPlacement was in the center of 4 hills.

Environment and its influence

A simple screening technique to identify rice genotypes with low photorespiration

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C₃ and C₄ plants are known to differ sharply in their response to physical factors such as light, temperature, and oxygen concentration. Physical conditions largely govern the efficiency of the physiological and biochemical parameters that control the growth processes. Adverse physical stresses such as high temperature, light intensity, or oxygen concentration enhance photorespiration and impose a premium on net photosynthetic efficiency for productivity in C₃ plants.

Gangadharan and Kleinhofs have used those stress parameters in a screen-

ing technique to isolate barley and wheat genotypes that are more efficient in net photosynthesis. Only the two stress parameters oxygen and light are now used for rice.

A plexiglass chamber, 1.5 × 0.6 × 0.6 m was placed on a zinc tray filled with water, with outlet and inlet. A measured quantity of oxygen was let in daily for about 10 minutes through a flowmeter at 2 liters/ minute from an oxygen cylinder after the chamber was filled with atmospheric air so that the enriched air had an oxygen concentration of 25-26%. A mercury light continuously lighted the chamber at night to give a light intensity of 25-26 klux. A thermometer held through the ceiling of the chamber recorded temperature. Earthen pots, 10 cm in diameter, with 10 seedlings (aged 15-20 days) each, were kept on the tray in water. Four pots of maize seedlings were also dis-

tributed as checks for screening.

The seedlings turned pale and chlorotic after about 10 days and withered completely within 4 weeks. Some plants survived comparatively longer than others under high oxygen concentration. Data on seedling survival and photosynthetic rates after flowering and 3 days after oxygen enrichment in the chamber are in the table. Two runs were made on sets showing survival.

The preliminary observations clearly established variations in the rice genotypes' ability to withstand higher oxygen concentration under continuous light. These observations are relevant in that higher levels of oxygen inhibit the activity of the carboxylating enzyme (RuDP-carboxylase) and enhance RuDP oxygenase activity. Obviously photorespiration was enhanced under high oxygen levels. Genotypes with low oxygenase activity even at high oxygen level